

Determination of Silver and Mercury with *p*-(2-Mercaptopropionamido) Benzoic Acid as a Gravimetric Reagent.

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Manuscript received 19 August 1976, revised 17 March 1977, accepted 21 March 1977

p-(2-Mercaptopropionamido) benzoic acid is a selective reagent for the gravimetric determination of Ag(I) and Hg(II) at pH 0.3 to 4.8. The reagent offers the advantages of ease of preparation, keeping qualities in the solid form and solubility in aqueous medium.

MERCAPTOACETAMIDES¹⁻³ and 2-Mercaptopropionamides⁴ are valuable reagents for the determination of some of the sulphide forming metals, however, many of these reagents have the shortcoming of low solubility in water. It was felt that the condensation product of 2-Mercaptopropionic acid and 4-aminobenzoic acid would overcome this shortcoming and might afford quantitative and selective precipitation of some of the cations at low pH. The reagent, indeed, fairly meets these requirements. It complexes with the sulphide forming cations to form precipitates which are in most cases soluble in the hot acid medium. Ag(I) and Hg(II) are, however, precipitated quantitatively in the pH range 0.3 to 4.8. Cu(II) interferes with their determination but it can be masked with EDTA. As such, the reagent can be used for the selective determinations of Ag(I) and Hg(II). The solubility of the reagent, even at low pH, is sufficient so that there is no contamination of the precipitates. The composition of the complexes suggests the following structure².

Compared to many a organic precipitant⁵ which has been thus far reported for the gravimetric determinations of Ag(I) and Hg(II), the use of the present reagent is extremely advantageous in view of its very simple preparation, keeping qualities in the solid form, solubility in aqueous medium and selectivity of reaction.

Experimental

Preparation of the Reagent.

Equimolecular quantities of 2-Mercaptopropionic acid and 4-aminobenzoic acid were refluxed in an

atmosphere of carbon dioxide at different temperatures ranging between 120° to 170° for different periods of time. Maximum yield of the product was obtained by refluxing for 4½ hours at 140° to 150°. 2-Mercaptopropionic acid (5 ml., Kochlight) and 4-aminobenzoic acid (7.5 g.) were refluxed for 4½ hours by heating in a bath of medicinal paraffin maintained at 140° to 150°. The melt was allowed to solidify and then ground with 25% HCl to remove the unreacted 4-aminobenzoic acid. The crude product weighed 6.6 g. It was recrystallized from benzene-ethanol (2 : 1). The colourless powder melted at 219°-220°, C₁₀H₁₁O₃NS requires: N, 6.22%, S, 14.23%. Found: N, 6.01%, S, 13.82%.

Solutions of Ag(I) and Hg(II)

The solutions were prepared by dissolving AnalaR, B.D.H. samples of silver nitrate and mercuric chloride. Standardization of the solutions was carried out by precipitating as chloride and sulphide respectively. Aliquots were then diluted to prepare 0.15% solutions.

Reagent Solution

Because the solution is susceptible to serial oxidation, fresh solution (0.5%) prepared by dissolving the required amount of the solid in hot ethanol and diluting with 9 parts of hot water was used.

Procedure for the Determination of Ag(I) and Hg(II)

Twenty ml. of the solution of the cation to be estimated was taken in a beaker and diluted to about 125 ml. Required amount of 2 N nitric acid in the case of silver and 2 N hydrochloric acid in the case of mercury was introduced to adjust the pH at 1 to 2. The solution was heated on a steam bath and the reagent solution was introduced dropwise with constant stirring. The precipitate, thus obtained, was digested for about 45 minutes, filtered through a sintered glass crucible G 3, washed with hot water to remove any adhering reagent, dried to a constant weight at 110°

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF Ag(I) AND Hg(II) IN PRESENCE OF DIVERSE IONS. (30 mg. OF THE METALS TAKEN FOR THEIR RESPECTIVE DETERMINATIONS).

Diverse ion	Amount added mg.	Wt. of Ag complex mg.	Ag found mg.	Error mg.	Wt. of Hg complex mg.	Hg Found mg.	Error mg.
—	—	92.0	29.90	-0.10	97.2	30.04	+0.04
—	—	91.8	29.84	-0.16	97.0	29.98	-0.02
—	—	92.4	30.03	+0.03	97.0	29.98	-0.02
—	—	92.4	30.03	+0.03	97.0	29.98	-0.02
Na(I), K(I)	100	92.8	30.15	+0.15	96.0	29.67	-0.3
NH ₄ (I)	100	92.0	29.90	-0.10	96.8	29.92	-0.08
Ca(II), Ba(II)	100	92.4	30.03	+0.03	96.8	29.92	-0.08
Sr(II), Mg(II)	100	92.4	30.03	+0.03	97.2	30.04	+0.04
Zn(II)	100	92.4	30.03	+0.03	97.0	29.98	-0.02
Mn(II)	100	92.8	30.15	+0.15	97.0	29.98	-0.02
Co(II)	100	92.4	30.09	+0.09	97.0	29.98	-0.02
Ni(II)	100	92.6	30.32	+0.23	97.6	30.16	+0.16
Al(III)	100	93.0	30.23	+0.23	97.6	30.16	+0.16
Cr(III)	100	92.6	30.09	+0.09	98.0	30.29	+0.29
Fe(III)	100	91.4	29.70	-0.30	97.0	29.98	-0.02
As(III)	100	—	—	—	97.0	29.98	-0.02
Sb(III)	100	—	—	—	97.2	30.04	+0.04
Cd(II)	100	92.4	30.03	+0.03	97.0	29.98	-0.02
Pb(II)	100	92.0	29.90	-0.10	96.6	29.86	-0.14
Bi(III)	100	93.0	30.23	+0.23	97.2	30.04	+0.04
Cu(II) ^a	50	92.8	30.15	+0.15	97.2	30.04	+0.04
Tl(I)	25	92.0	29.90	-0.01	96.8	29.92	-0.08
Th(IV)	25	92.4	30.03	-0.03	97.0	29.98	-0.02
Zr(IV)	25	92.4	30.03	+0.03	96.8	29.92	-0.08
UO ₂ (II)	25	92.6	30.09	+0.09	97.2	30.04	+0.04
VO ₂ (II)	25	92.4	30.03	+0.03	97.2	30.04	+0.04
Ce(IV)	25	92.8	30.15	+0.15	96.6	29.86	-0.14
Molybdate ^b	50	92.4	30.03	+0.03	96.8	29.92	-0.08
Tungstate ^b	50	92.4	30.03	+0.03	97.2 ^c	30.04	+0.04

^a Masked with EDTA at pH 4.8.

^b In the determination of silver in the presence of molybdate and tungstate, EDTA was used at pH 4.8 to prevent the precipitation of the corresponding salts.

^c The determination was carried out at pH 4.8.

and weighed. The weights of the complexes multiplied by 0.3250 and 0.3090 give the weights of silver and mercury respectively.

Determinations in the Presence of Diverse Ions

Alkali metals, alkaline earths, ammonium, Zn(II), Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Fe(III), Cd(II), Pb(II), Bi(III), Tl(I), Th(IV), Zr(IV), VO₂(II), UO₂(II), molybdate and tungstate do not interfere with the determinations of Ag(I) and Hg(II). The interference due to Cu(II) can be prevented by masking it with EDTA. In the determination of silver in the presence of molybdate and tungstate, EDTA prevents the precipitation of the corresponding salts. Though the determination of mercury in the presence of Sb(III) and As(III) was carried out, that of silver in their presence was not possible because these cations were available only as chlorides.

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